

Multi-channel electroluminescence of CdTe/CdS core-shell quantum dots

implemented into a QLED device

A. Pidluzhna,^a K. Ivaniuk,^a P. Stakhira,^a Z. Hotra,^{a,b} M. Chapran,^c J. Ulanski,^c

O.Tynkevych,^d Y. Khalavka,^d G. V. Baryshnikov,^{e,f} B. F. Minaev,^e H. Ågren^{f,g}

^a*Lviv Polytechnic National University, Stepan Bandera 12, 79013 Lviv, Ukraine*

^b*Rzeszow University of Technology, al. Powstańców Warszawy 12, 35-959 Rzeszów, Poland*

^c*Department of Molecular Physics, Lodz University of Technology,*

Zeromskiego 116, 90-924 Lodz, Poland

^d*Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, Kotsiubynsky Str. 2, Chernivtsi 58012, Ukraine*

^e*Department of Chemistry and Nanomaterials Science,*

Bohdan Khmelnytsky National University, 18031, Cherkasy, Ukraine

^f*Division of Theoretical Chemistry and Biology, School of Engineering Sciences in Chemistry,*

Biotechnology and Health, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 10691 Stockholm, Sweden

^g*Department of Physics and Astronomy, Uppsala University, Box 516, SE-751 20 Uppsala, Sweden.*

Abstract

CdTe/CdS core-shell quantum dots were synthesized and implemented into a light emitting device resulting in multi-channel electroluminescence with a light-green emission colour. The main electroluminescence band at about 530 nm corresponds to the emission by the CdTe core (type I core/shell structure), while the next emission band at 595 nm is assigned to the crossed recombination of electrons from the conduction band of the CdS shell and holes from the valence band of the CdTe core (type II core/shell structure). At the same time, the photoluminescence spectrum of the synthesized CdTe/CdS core-shell quantum dots contains only one emission band distinctive for type II structures. This behavior of CdTe/CdS core-shell quantum dots upon the electroexcitation allows the extension of the electroluminescence spectrum in the optical region in a way that is useful for the lighting-source applications. Such multi-channel electroluminescence can most probably also be reproduced in related core-shell systems accounting for size-confinement between the core size and shell thickness.

Keywords: quantum dots, core-shell structures, electroluminescence, photoluminescence, QLED.

1. Introduction

The strong exciton binding energy in quasi-one dimensional quantum dots (QD) enables the effect of quantum confinement [1, 2]. The significant role of topology and geometrical parameters on the QD band structure and emission spectra has attracted a considerable interest for practical device applications over the last 20 years. In particular, the promising applications of QDs in the next generation display and lighting technology, such as QD-based light emitting diodes (QLEDs), has generated a major research effort [3-5]. Implantation of QDs in electroluminescence emitter devices provides narrow spectra with high color purity and tunable emission wavelengths via varying the quantum dot size, composition and operational stability [6-8]. Moreover, QLEDs can readably be fabricated by solution processes such as spin coating, blade coating and inkjet printing techniques, which is an important aspect for reducing the cost of mass production [9]. Typically QLEDs are made in sandwich structures, where the quantum dots are stacked between the classical organic hole transport (HTL) and electron transport (ETL) layers. Under electrical excitation, carriers are injected in the emitting layer, where they confine and produce radiative recombination. In order to obtain high quantum efficiency in OLEDs one thus needs to understand charge carrier recombination and light generation processes in the QD layers.

During the latter years many efficient methods for synthesis of QDs with homogeneous size and favorable optical properties have been proposed [10, 11]. A new trend in LED industry has implied a shift from methods of synthesis that involve toxic organic solvents towards the use of aqueous media [12-14]. Considering some complications referring to solution based deposition of QD layers, and as a result device performance degradation [5, 15-19], the application of aqueous solutions in QLED technology has to date though not been widely used. One of the methods to avoid the above-mentioned “aqueous medium” problem is the fabrication of light emitting devices with application of inorganic/organic heterostructural components. Particularly, in such devices the coating of QD from aqueous solutions onto an inorganic hole transport layer (HTL) like MoO_3 [20, 21] is accomplished at the initial stages of the QLED formation. The following steps of this formation involve a technique of thermovacuum deposition for organic semiconductive films or spin-coating from organic solutions.

In the current study we have presented an implementation of CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs synthesized by a precipitation method from an aqueous medium into the QLED device with a quite simple layered scheme. The fabricated device demonstrates not extraordinary lighting characteristics but very unusual multi-channel electroluminescence (EL) which is principally different from the photoluminescence (PL) spectrum of the same multilayered system as well as from the free QD. There is thus a fundamental difference between the EL and PL phenomena of

CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs due to the different pathways for the population of corresponding excited states responsible for the emission process. In this case, the EL spectrum is richer than the PL one and contains at least three bands of different origin that is important for extending the emission spectrum into the blue and red regions comparing with the single-band deep-orange PL of the QDs both in aqueous solutions and in solid films. This phenomenon is fundamentally important because it can be realized for the related core-shell QDs and corresponding QLEDs with simplified structure and improved efficiency as well.

2. Experiments and Methods

Core/shell CdTe/CdS quantum dots were synthesized at room temperature in alkali aqueous solution by the precipitation reaction of CdSO₄ and freshly prepared H₂Te (Figure 1) according to the method reported by Rogach et al. [13]. Thioglycolic acid was used as a stabilizing agent for the QDs. Hydrogen telluride was produced by the electrochemical method of tellurium reduction on the tellurium cathode. The oxygen dissolved in the reaction media was removed from the system by an argon flow during 10 min.

Figure 1. Preparation scheme for core/shell CdTe/CdS quantum dots stabilized by thioglycolic acid (TGA).

In more details, 4.4 g 3CdSO₄×8H₂O was dissolved in 1 l of water in a three-neck round-bottom flask and 2 ml of thioglycolic acid was injected into the solution. The pH was adjusted up to 11 using 1 M NaOH solution. Obtained cadmium precursor solution was bubbled with freshly prepared hydrogen telluride for 10 min. Finally, the flask was connected to a condenser and refluxed at 100° C for 8 h.

All chemicals were of analytical grade obtained from Sigma-Aldrich: 3CdSO₄×8H₂O (purity ≥ 99.0 %); thioglycolic acid (purity ≥ 98 %); NaOH (purity ≥ 99 purity); tellurium granular (99.99 % trace metals basis).

The average size of the CdTe quantum dots prepared at this stage is about 2.3±0.3nm in accordance with the TEM data [22] and spectroscopic measurements [13]. To provide growth and stabilization of a CdS shell around the CdTe QD freshly obtained solution of CdTe QD was

kept at 100°C for 8 h. The resulting size of the CdTe/CdS quantum dots is about 3.3 nm that follows from optical spectroscopy data and cyclic voltammetry measurements [23]. Because the average size of the CdTe core is about 2.3 nm and the thickness of a 1 monolayer (ML) CdS shell is estimated to be about 0.35 nm [24], the average shell thickness around the CdTe core is estimated to 0.5 nm, which means that the CdS shell grows by about 1.4 ML. These data are closely similar to those published by Wang et. al for the same type of CdTe/CdS core/shell quantum dots [25].

Absorption spectra were recorded with a Carry 5000 (Varian) spectrometer. Photoluminescence spectra of solution and thin films prepared by spin-coating were performed at room temperature with an Edinburgh Instruments FLS980 fluorescence spectrometer with an Xe-lamp as an excitation source and R-928 photomultiplier detector. The photoluminescence quantum yields (PLQY) of the blends were measured using a calibrated integrating sphere from Edinburgh Instruments. Fluorescence lifetimes were recorded using time-resolved a photon counting (SPC) method and an EPLED 340 nm picosecond pulsed light emitting diode as an excitation source.

A spin-coating technique was used for the deposition of QDs active layer by dropcasting of 5 ml QDs aqueous solution (3 mg/ml) onto the ITO/glass substrate with MoO₃ layer and rotating at 1500 rpm for 30 sec and 3000 rpm for next 60 sec. Then the samples were dried at 100C for 30 min. Thermovacuum deposited MoO₃ was as used as the hole injector layer [20, 26] and TPBi as an organic semiconductor electron transport layer [21, 27]. Ca and Al metal electrodes were disposed onto a precleaned ITO-coated glass surface under a vacuum of 10⁻⁵ Torr. The overall scheme for the constructed QLED was ITO/MoO₃(10nm)/QD(20nm)/TPBi(50nm)/ Ca(20nm)/Al(150nm). The thickness of thin films was controlled and determined by means of a profilometer (Dektak XT, Bruker). Density-voltage and luminescence-voltage dependences were measured using a semiconductor parameter analyzer HP4145A. The measurement of brightness was obtained using a calibrated photodiode [28] and the electroluminescence spectra were recorded with an Ocean Optics USB2000 spectrometer.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Photoluminescence spectra and decay kinetics.

The absorption spectrum of the CdTe/CdS QD aqueous solution shows a distinctive band at about 550 nm corresponding to the 1s-1s electronic transition in the CdTe core. This assignment is in agreement with the published sizing curve [13]: the 1s-1s absorption at 550 nm corresponds to an average size of ~2.5 nm for the CdTe QDs (2.3±0.3nm in the current study).

The photoluminescence spectra of the CdTe/CdS core/shell QD aqueous solution and thick film contain only a single emission band at about 580 and 590 nm, respectively (Figure 2a). The 10 nm energy shift can be attributed to an aggregation effect upon the formation of the continuous thick film if compared to the aqueous solution and thin film spectra. The emission spectra of the solution and films stay the same at the different excitation wavelengths. It should be noted also that the PL spectra of the thin film and of the aqueous solution are identical (Figure 2a). The photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) for the aqueous solution of CdTe/CdS core/shell QD samples equals to 39% and for spin-coated thin film - 17%.

Figure 2. UV-Vis absorption spectrum of CdTe/CdS core/shell QD in aqueous solution and photoluminescence (PL) spectra of QD solution and thin/thick films.

It is well known fact that CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs can be divided into two categories based on their potential structures: type-I and type-II QDs [29-32]. In type-I QDs, electrons and holes are confined to the same space in the CdTe core, i.e. the electron-hole recombination occurs just in the core. However, in type-II QDs, holes and electrons are spatially separated due to the type-II band alignment (holes are in the CdTe core, while electrons reside in the CdS shell). That is the reason for that the luminescence of type-II CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs occurs through the recombination of electrons from the conduction band (CB) of the CdS shell and holes from the valence band (VB) of the CdTe core (Figure 2b). It provides a distinctive red shift of the main luminescence band for the CdTe/CdS core/shell system comparing with the same size CdTe QD without shell. The time-resolved transient absorption spectroscopy experiments carried out by Wang et. al. [25] directly shows that the CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs gradually developed from quasi-type-I to type-II as the shell thickness is increased from 0.3 to 1.6 ML (e.g. from 0.1 to 0.55 nm). The quasi-type-I system means that the hole is localized in the core, and that the electron is localized not exactly in the core but delocalized over the whole nanocrystal because of the very small size of the shell. Considering the quite thick CdS shell

(0.5 nm) around the CdTe core (2.3 nm) the CdTe/CdS quantum dots correspond in our case to the type-II systems. Thus, for both aqueous solution and thin solid film the emission at 580 nm (Figure 2a) is attributed to the recombination of electrons from the CB of the CdS shell and holes from the VB of the CdTe core through the initial intermediate nonradiative transfer of an electron from the CB of the CdTe to the CB of the CdS shell (dashed arrow in Figure 2b).

The PL decay in the plain CdTe core is usually well fitted by the biexponential functions. Wang et. al. [25] have established PL lifetimes equal to 1.3 ns (71%) and 7.2 ns (29%) for the 2.1 nm CdTe QD in aqueous solution. Close similar data were published by Zeng et al. [33] for 1.5 nm CdTe species (1.3 ns (63%) and 7.3 (37%)), while for the larger QDs of 3 nm size the PL lifetimes are slightly higher – being equal to 2.0 ns (45%) and 10.3 ns (55%). The fast PL decay component corresponds expectedly to an exciton recombination, while the slow component most likely originates from the surface-related emission or the emission of dark excitons [33-35].

The PL decay curves of the two CdTe/CdS QD samples measured in this work for the thin film (Figure 3a) and aqueous solution (Figure 3b) at the photoluminescence band maxima (580 nm) also fit well with the biexponential functions (Table 1) similar to the bare CdTe QDs. However, in contrast to the PL decay components of core-shell samples are definitely longer than that of the bare CdTe QDs. It happens due to a delocalization of the electron in the CdS shell (type-II system behavior). From the quantum theory point of view the spatial separation of the electron in the shell and the hole in the core provides the decreasing of overlapping between the hole and electron wave function that corresponds to the longer radiative lifetime [33]. The hole-electron separation also decreases the probability of surface-related emission, and thus the slow component of the PL decay for the core-shell system becomes two-three times longer relative to the bare CdTe QDs.

Figure 3. Photoluminescence transients measured at the photoluminescence band maxima of QDs in film (a) and in aqueous solution (b). Blue line depicts the fitting curve by two single exponential decay components ($\lambda_{\text{Ex}}=340$ nm).

Table 1. Fitting results of the photoluminescence transients and photophysical constants of the CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs aqueous solution and thin solid film ($\lambda_{ex}=340$ nm).

Sample	QY	χ^2	τ_1 , ns	B_1 , %	τ_2 , ns	B_2 , %	τ_{av} , ns	τ_r , ns	k_r , s ⁻¹	k_{nr} , s ⁻¹
Solid film	0.17	1.275	8.16	7.8	20.7	92.3	20.3	119	8.4×10^6	4.1×10^7
Aqueous solution	0.39	1.123	7.47	7.8	25.12	92.3	24.7	63	1.6×10^7	2.5×10^7

Herein we have also estimated the main photophysical constants of the QDs using the following relations:

$$PLQY = \frac{k_r}{k_r + k_{nr}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{av}} = k_r + k_{nr}, \quad (2)$$

where k_r and k_{nr} are the rate constants for the radiative and non-radiative processes, τ_{av} is the average PL lifetime estimated through the τ_1 and τ_2 time constants and B_1 and B_2 amplitudes of the components [36]:

$$\tau_{av} = \frac{B_1\tau_1^2 + B_2\tau_2^2}{B_1\tau_1 + B_2\tau_2} \quad (3)$$

The radiative lifetime for the studied CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs equals 63 and 119 ns for the aqueous solution and thin solid film samples that correspond to the PL rate constants of 1.6×10^7 and 8.4×10^6 s⁻¹, respectively. These data are in a close agreement with published values [33] for the similar size CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs. Accounting for the fact that the PLQY depends on the aggregation state and that it equals about 39% in aqueous solution and 17% in the solid state, the nonradiative rate constant k_{nr} has been estimated to 2.5×10^7 and 4.1×10^7 for aqueous solution and thin film, respectively.

Having established the type-II behavior of the synthesized CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs it is interesting to test them as an active layer in QLED compositions and investigate how the emission properties of the type-II QDs depend on the excitation source (photoexcitation vs. electroexcitation), see below.

3.2. QLED characterization

The overall construction scheme and energy diagram of the fabricated QLED are presented in Figures 4a and 4b, respectively. The energies of the conduction and valence band edges (vs. vacuum) were adopted as -2.3 and -5.3 eV for the MoO₃ hole transporting layer [20, 26,37], -2.1 and -5.4 eV for the TPBi electron transporting layer (ETL) [38], -3.7 and -5.7 eV for the CdTe/CdS QD of 3.3 nm size [23]. The electron and hole workout for the ITO anode and

Ca:Al cathode were taken as -4.7 and -2.9 eV, respectively [39]. MoO₃ was chosen as a HTL to decrease the barrier for hole injection. In combination with the well known ETL and hole blocking TPBi layer, the exciton structure of the QLED could be confirmed.

As can be seen from CIE1931 chromaticity diagram (Figure 4c), the fabricated device possesses the overall light-green color which corresponds to the electroluminescence (EL) spectrum presented in Figure 5a (red line). This spectrum contains three broad bands with maxima at 420, 530 and 595 nm in great contrast to the single band PL emission with maximum at 580 and 590 nm for the thin and thick solid film, respectively. The EL spectrum can be explained by the mixed type-I and type-II behavior of CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs upon the excitation by injection of holes and electrons into the QD active layers (Figure 5b). The most intensive EL band at 530 nm (arrow 1 in figure 5b) corresponds to the emissive recombination of holes and electrons in the CdTe core which is typical for type-I core-shell QDs [22]. The applied voltage induces a charge carrier transfer into the core overcoming the barrier between the CB of the CdS shell and the CdTe core (Figure 5b). However, the EL band at 530 nm is slightly blue shifted comparing with that band in the PL spectrum of CdTe/CdS QDs of the same size (545 nm [22], 560 nm [25]). That can probably be explained by the strain-induced band shift effect which means that the growth of CB edge level of the CdTe core is affected by the growing of the shell thickness [40]. The thicker the CdS shell the higher energy of the 1s-1s transition in CdTe core, e.g. the emission band of type-I CdTe/CdS QDs shifts to the blue region because of the strong strain effect of the CdS shell.

Figure 4. Principal scheme (a) and the energy diagram (b) for the fabricated QLED together with a CIE1931 chromaticity diagram (c) in which the black points corresponds to the color coordinates of the device and PL maximum of CdTe/CdS QDs in solid film.

The next EL band at 595 nm (arrow 2 in Figure 5b) corresponds to the distinctive band in the PL spectrum of the type-II CdTe/CdS core/shell QDs. It means that some part of electrons injected from the cathode is still localized in the CdS shell causing recombination with the holes from the CdTe core (type-II behavior). The weak EL band at 420 nm (arrow 3 in Figure 5b) most likely corresponds to the exciton emission of the CdS shell together with the emission of surface-localized traps [21].

Figure 5. The EL spectrum (at 15 V) of the fabricated device vs. the solid film PL spectrum of CdTe/CdS core/shell QD (a) and the proposed scheme of electroluminescence for the current QDs. The arrows 1, 2 and 3 correspond to the EL bands at 530, 595 and 420 nm respectively. The dashed line represents the trap level in this system.

The device characteristics are presented in Figure 6 and maximum values of efficiency are summarized in Table 2. The QLED exhibits a high turn-on voltage of 9 V and maximum brightness of 3100 cd/m² at 20V. The high turn-on voltage of the device can be explained by the presence of a significant barrier for hole transport between the HTL and the quantum dot emissive layers. The current efficiency, power efficiency and external quantum efficiency of the QLED were found to be 0.85 cd/A, 0.19 Lm/W and 0.4%, respectively. It is notable that the device demonstrates a stable current efficiency in a wide range of brightness from 1000 up to 3100 cd/m² (figure 6b). Also, the current and power efficiency are almost independent on the current density in the range from 30 to 350 mA/cm², which also suggests a high stability of the constructed QLED with respect to electrooxidation of the active QD layer with subsequent electrodegradation of the whole device.

Table 2. Summary of QLED performance

Device	V_{on} , V	Max brightness at 20 V, cd/m^2	Max current efficiency, cd/A	Max power efficiency, lm/W	Max external quantum efficiency, %	CIE coordinates
QLED	9.0	3100	0.85	0.19	0.4	0.351;0.418
QLED [44]	8.0	53.7	-	-	-	-

Figure 6. Current density-voltage, brightness-voltage (a) and current efficiency-brightness characteristic (b) for ITO/MoO₃(10nm)/QD(20nm)/TPBi(50nm)/Ca(20nm)/Al(150nm) QLED.

It is important to note, that fabricated device indeed demonstrates the mixed type-I and type-II behaviour of CdTe/CdS core-shell QDs upon electroexcitation that allows to significantly extend the EL spectrum into the green-blue region. Incorporation of an additional stable blue-emissive layer into the proposed multilayered QLED should affect the resulting white emission colour [41-43]. The fabrication of such a WQLED device is an upcoming task in our group.

We should also note that this is not the first attempt to fabricate QLEDs based on CdTe/CdS core-shell quantum dots. Previously, Molaei and Pourjafari [44] utilized such kind of QDs (the core size is about 6 nm and 2 nm CdS shell surrounds the CdTe core) in a similar ITO/MoO₃/PVK/QDs/Mg:Ag QLED. However, due to the relatively high thickness of the CdS shell and large size of the whole QDs their QLED demonstrates only one EL band at 600 nm that corresponds to the type-II core-shell system. Most likely, this is again due to the strain-induced shift of the CB in the CdTe core. This effect provides a high energy barrier between the CBs of CdS and CdTe and thus the injected electrons can not migrate into the CdTe core but remain localized in the shell providing the emissive recombination with the holes from the CdTe core (distinctive type-II behavior). Therefore we can conclude that the mixing of the type-I and type-II electron-hole recombination pathways and thus the broadening of the EL spectrum profile can

be observed only for small CdTe/CdS core-shell quantum dots (about 3-3.5 nm) with a moderate thickness of the CdS shell (about 1.5 ML).

4. Conclusions

The fact that inclusion of quantum dots in electroluminescence emitter devices provides great potential possibilities to obtain narrow spectra with color purity and high tunability we have studied in the present work the operability and use of small core/shell QDs in an organic light-emitting device (OLED). Small core/shell CdTe/CdS quantum dots synthesized by a precipitation method and stabilized by thioglycolic acid were used as the OLED emission layer. A spin-coating technique for the deposition of QD from the aqueous solution combined with the thermovacuum deposition of transporting layers has been used. The resulting electroluminescence spectrum contains three main emission bands that correspond to multichannel radiation through different electron-hole recombination pathways. Comparing the electroluminescence spectrum of the device with the photoluminescence spectra of thin and thick film core/shell CdTe/CdS quantum dots we can conclude that they can possess only type II behavior upon photoexcitation and mixed type I/II behavior upon electroexcitation, i.e. upon voltage-induced injection of holes and electrons into the active layer. This is the first observation of mixed type I/II behavior for the thin-shell CdTe/CdS quantum dots. Such effects can probably also be observed for related core/shell systems like CdTe/ZnS, CdSe/CdS and provide a possible pathway to improve current OLED devices with respect to performance and color quality.

Acknowledgments

The calculations were performed with computational resources provided by the High Performance Computing Center North (HPC2N) which is a Swedish national center for Scientific and Parallel Computing through the project “Multiphysics Modeling of Molecular Materials” SNIC 2017-12-49. The study was also supported by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (projects no. 0118U003862, 0117U003908 and 0118U000268), by Carl Tryggers foundation (Grant No. CTS 17:514) and Olle Engkvist Byggmästare foundation (contract No. 189-0223). M.C. and J.U. are grateful for financial support from grant 674990 EXCILIGHT-H2020-MSCA-ITN-2015.

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